

Utilizing Data Control and Resource Reservation for AI Image Matching with Satellite Imagery Using Long-Short Term Memory Model to Detect Flooding

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RIFFAI is an advanced AI model designed to detect signs of flooding by leveraging various data sources and analytical techniques including satellite imagery databased, image matching point distribution, forecasted weather. The model continuously receives real-time satellite imagery. This imagery provides up-to-date visual information about the Earth's surface, allowing the model to monitor water bodies, land cover, and changes in terrain that may indicate flooding. The study detects flood areas using a decision fusion method and analyzes the effects on a macro scale, particularly focusing on land use and land cover.

Figure 1. Flood detection and multi-scale analysis framework. Source: Phonekham et. al (2023)

RIFFAI employs NDVI (Vegetation), NDWI (Water), MNDWI (Normalized Water) in detecting flooding through satellite imagery and GIS layers. These indices provide a framework for monitoring environmental changes and identifying flood events with little time window. To simplify, when the vegetation decreases, and water increases from normal water, there's a high likeliness that there's a flood in that location and time.

RIFFAI leverages Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for image classification and processing, which offers a more refined and accurate analysis compared to other competitors using physics-based (language-based) models. Additionally, our Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model enables us to manage and control data more effectively, preventing information overload while still making precise predictions. This approach ensures that our predictions are not just accurate but also timely, which is crucial in climate resilience and early warning systems. With the use of CNN and LSTM model to detect patterns of environment changes occur in satellite imagery. RIFFAI can detect flooding, coastal change, vegetation, and wildfire.

To illustrate the results, the validation results of the LSTM model forecasting NDVI, NDWI, and MNDWI are 0.6916 for R-squared and 0.004 for Mean Squared Error[2], 0.7027 for R-

squared and 0.00058 for Mean Squared Error[3], and 0.6092 for R-squared and 0.0029 for Mean Squared Error[4], respectively. Therefore, the overall accuracy of the LSTM model is 0.6678 for R-squared and 0.00249 for Mean Squared Error. Furthermore, RIFFAI seeks to improve the LSTM model for forecasting NDVI, NDWI, and MNDWI by appending additional features and altering the parameters inside the model.

Figure 2. The graph compares the predicted values using the LSTM model versus the real NDVI values and shows the validation results.

Figure 3. The graph compares the predicted values using the LSTM model versus the real NDWI values and shows the validation results.

Figure 4. The graph compares the predicted values using the LSTM model versus the real MNDWI values and shows the validation results.

In conclusion, RIFFAI demonstrates the potential of integrating advanced AI techniques, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, to effectively detect and predict flooding events using satellite imagery and environmental indices. By leveraging key indices like NDVI, NDWI, and MNDWI, RIFFAI can monitor shifts in vegetation and water coverage, offering an early detection system for floods, coastal changes, and other environmental hazards. The model's use of LSTM ensures precise, timely predictions by managing data efficiently, which is critical for climate resilience and disaster preparedness. Validation results highlight the accuracy of the LSTM model, although there is room for improvement through feature enhancement and parameter tuning. Overall, RIFFAI contributes a robust and scalable tool for environmental monitoring and flood prediction, with ongoing development aimed at increasing the precision and applicability of the system across various geographic regions.

Reference

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